

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES OF GENDER CONFLICT RESOLUTION IN THE FAMILY

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Abstract: Currently, when analyzing relationships, both at the social and labor level, gender equality is not disputed, but at the same time, many social sciences pay great attention to such a problem as gender self-determination

Keywords: Gender, conflict, gender, conflicts, equality, society, dimorphism, determination.

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In psychology, the concept of gender is defined as the polarity of a male and female subject, which is evaluated not from the point of view of a biological species, but as an element of society in which individual individuals function and interact[2].

From the point of view of L.V. Mishchenko, in biology, the division into men and women is based on such a concept as gender or gender identity. This means that the division of the entire number of people is carried out on the basis of primary and secondary sexual characteristics, that is, on the basis of sexual dimorphism.

In the conditions of society, the separation is carried out not so much on the basis of biological aspects as on the basis of a person's personality, that is, the separation is based on gender differences between men and women. Exploring the concepts of gender, it is impossible to put an equal sign between the definition of gender and gender, since if sexual dimorphism is represented by clear criteria and can be assigned only to a man or only to a woman, socially gender has a wider range of characteristics. This leads to the fact that gender, although it is a "synonym" for the concept of "gender", but its application is carried out to denote the natural or social manifestation of the male or female sex, this concept can also be used as part of the opposition to the biological sex[3].

An adult can determine his own gender and the factors associated with it. At the same time, taking into account the level of development of society and science, he can not rely on a biological trait, but only on the level of his own gender development[4].

We can agree with this statement with the caveat that gender self-determination is associated not so much with the desire to change one's gender, as with the desire to change the perception of gender as a biological species, with the types of behavior and reaction inherent in each species. This is due to the stereotypes formed over the course of the development of society in the reaction, behavior and psyche of each sex, which, with the development of sociology, to one degree or another were transferred to the gender associated with this sex.

Also, it cannot be denied that from the point of view of psychology, the concept of "gender" is defined as a socio-biological characteristic of an individual, with the help of which society defines concepts such as "man" and "woman". With this in mind, many social psychologists define gender differences between men and women on the basis of biological perception of gender, using this as sexual differentiation[5].

Based on this, it can be concluded that there is currently a need to form an integrated approach to the study of gender and behavior of men and women, as a complex system that has many levels of structure and an ambiguous system of connections. The use of this approach will make it possible to form a "multidimensional, multilevel, multidimensional determination, including phenomena of different orders" [6].

This will allow us to deepen the knowledge that exists at the present time in the field of studying gender and gender behavior and will allow us to more fully use the results obtained in all areas of the study of social interaction in general, and in conflictology in particular.

The study of gender relations is increasingly moving into the focus of the study of the humanities and social sciences, which reduces the degree of influence of stereotypical and biological perception of gender as a factor determining human behavior and motivation. At the same time, we must not forget that different sciences perceive gender self-determination differently, determine its importance and, as a result, the sensitivity of including gender aspects in the field of research.

This is due to the fact that in sociology the concept of gender began to separate from the concept of biological sex in order to determine the principles of building interaction between individuals.

At the same time, significant attention is paid to such aspects of interaction as building relationships, conflicts, grouping, developing the perception of the opposite gender and transferring certain aspects of behavior to the group and society, in accordance with the gender self-determination of an individual and a group of individuals.

It is also worth noting the statement of T. Bulavina, who in her writings notes that “the most intensive dissemination of gender studies occurs through sociology”[7].

If we consider the inclusion of the gender factor in the study of social intelligence by foreign authors in the field of sociology, it is necessary to note the work of such scientists as G. Alloport, J. Guilford and G. Eysenck. They did not agree on the definition of gender and its impact on human social behavior.

The problems of gender relations from the point of view of the division of gender roles in work in particular and in society as a whole were carried out in the works of E. Durkheim. From his point of view, the developed differentiation, both in cultural differences and in physical differences between men and women, increases with the development of society, although from the point of view of the formation of social intelligence, this process should have the opposite direction[8].

The presence of internal psychological problems or unsettled personal life is transferred to labor relations, in the form of splashing out negative emotions on others, as well as in the form of transferring attitudes to a certain person, to the entire group of persons who have the same signs.

In case of increased vulnerability, a woman in a situation of stress and depression not only shifts the entire focus of her attention to solving the problem, but also tries to focus her environment on this at all levels of interaction with society.

When stress levels increase, men try to isolate themselves from negative reactions and experiences, switching their focus to solving work or personal problems that are not related to a stressful situation.

It cannot be said that this tactic is optimal, since in the future, the accumulated deferred stress will lead to a more aggressive reaction in the event of an increased stressful situation or the development of stress in another area of their lives. As a result, the conflict will develop exponentially without an objective assessment of the conflict factor[9].

This type of behavior is present in people who are in adulthood, have sufficiently developed social intelligence, and also have the necessary resources and skills to manage their emotions and behavior in stressful and conflict situations. At the same time, the gender factor still continues to play a significant role, determining the order of reaction to stress and conflict.

Gender self-determination in adolescents is in an undeveloped state, which is associated with an immature psyche and a low level of social intelligence. Accordingly, their reaction to the conflict, which is based on the gender factor, is more pronounced. However, in this case, the gender factor is taken into account in a negative way and does not allow finding a solution to the conflict situation. This

leads to the suppression of the conflict, which further shifts it from the focus of attention of the party that can influence the course and development of the conflict.

If we evaluate the behavior of girls and boys in a conflict situation, it is worth noting that the female sex has a high predisposition to the development of relationships, building communication links and forming a clear attitude to certain situations.

Young men in adolescence have a need for dominance, which is reflected in the principles of building social relationships. In this situation, the level of social intelligence is lower than that of the female sex. In the situation of the development of the conflict "young man / young man", the solution of the conflict situation occurs faster than in the situation "young man / girl", which is due precisely to the motives of the behavior of young people, as well as the level of development of social intelligence [10].

This allows us to confirm the need to take gender into account when implementing conflict resolution in the youth environment, without taking into account the behavior patterns of men and women adopted or imposed on society. The solution of the conflict without taking into account gender leads to the use of the tactics of "give in", "be wiser", "what to take from him". In fact, this is not a solution to the conflict, but only fuels the gap between genders, preventing the formation of an objective perception of the principles of mutual relations in society, reinforcing social stereotypes and incorrect behavior in conflict situations.

In conflict resolution, the gender factor can often play a significant role. The reasons for this are that, taking into account the modern perception of a person's gender identity by modern society, regardless of whether it is a man or a woman, certain behavioral traits are attributed to each side, both in life and in a conflict situation.

There is a difference in the choice of a strategy of behavior in a conflict between men and women. Women tend to choose behavior that will not harm the existing relationship, instead of striving to achieve personal goals. Typical techniques may be offers of compromise, deals; actions to reduce hostility. On the contrary, men prefer to put pressure on the opponent, to show their dominance over him. Using the test of K. Thomas, a conclusion was made regarding gender differences in the choice of behavior strategies. Thus, faced with the impossibility of avoiding conflict, men will prefer open rivalry, and women are most likely to choose adaptation[11].

M.M. Kashapova and T.G. Shalaeva, when diagnosing the leading type of reaction, note that "with "aggression", the expression of feelings and positions occurs with elements of rudeness, threats, demands or hostility combined with a small share of responsibility for the consequences of their actions"[12]. The

"withdrawal" is characterized by the cessation of communication, which inevitably leads to the "stagnation" of the problem, since it is not solved. An individual may experience feelings of confusion, anxiety, guilt.

When resolving a conflict taking into account gender, it is necessary to take into account the following factors[13]:

- the presence of a gender difference between the conflicting parties (the conflict occurs between a man and a woman, the conflict occurs between representatives of the same gender);
- the level of interpersonal relationships between the conflicting parties (the presence of family ties, labor relations, participation in the group);
- the cause of the conflict situation (gender conflict, other cause of conflict).

So in a situation of "resolving gender conflicts at the family level, in a situation where they arise between spouses, it is necessary to observe the following principles of relationships:

- maintain a sense of personal dignity of the spouse;
- control yourself in the manifestations of anger, irritation;
- do not focus on the partner's mistakes, do not remind them of them;
- to suspend the growing tension;
- do not torment yourself and your spouse with doubts about loyalty;
- do not forget about the need for patience, kindness, care and other positive qualities" [14].

In order to resolve the conflict constructively, married couples turn to mediation. In the process of working on the marital conflict, emphasis is placed on the existing common values of the spouses, common hobbies and interests. In addition, possible obstacles to the disclosure of individual potentials of family members are identified.

Among the gender differences, the differences in the manifestation of aggression are most clearly expressed. However, many authors indicate that, contrary to assumptions, the difference does not have a strong link to biological characteristics and is not as pronounced as previously assumed.

Who will be more aggressive in the conflict, a man or a woman, can be influenced by various factors: the gender of the opponent, the distinguishing feature of the problem.

"Society often dictates to men the need to show aggression, explaining this by the need to assert themselves, to defend their position in the social hierarchy. On the contrary, the same society can reproach women for openly expressing aggression. As a result, men prefer such social roles where they can behave "aggressively", while women consider such behavior unacceptable for themselves.

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